

Quantitative Estimation of Tegafur and Uracil in Capsule Dosage Form Using Statistical Modeling Assisted Analytical Methods

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ABSTRACT:

This research is focused on creating robust multivariate statistical regression models, specifically Principal Component Regression (PCR) and Partial Least Squares Regression (PLS), to accurately predict the concentrations of Tegafur and Uracil in capsule formulations. The goal was to develop reliable and efficient models for simultaneous estimation of these two components. Tegafur and Uracil are commonly used to treat colorectal cancer. This study employed UV-spectrophotometry combined with chemometric techniques for accurate drug estimation. Calibration curves for both drugs were constructed using methanol as a solvent at a maximum UV absorption at 270 nm for Tegafur and 258 nm for Uracil. Various synthetic mixtures of these drugs, within the concentration range of 3–18 $\mu\text{g/mL}$, were prepared and these mixtures were divided into calibration and validation sets to develop the chemometric models. Spectral data from these mixtures were processed using Unscrambler X software, and PCR and PLS models were developed. These models were used to predict the content of the drugs in Luporal capsules, a marketed formulation. Both drugs showed excellent linearity with R^2 values above 0.999 in the specified concentration range. The relationship between the concentration of the drugs and their spectral data was found to be highly linear, with a strong correlation coefficient ($R^2 > 0.999$) within the specified range. For the purpose of developing a chemometric model, a specific wavelength range (225–300 nm) with a 5 nm interval was chosen. The optimal number of factors for both PCR and PLS models was identified as 7. To assess the performance of these models, statistical metrics such as the root mean square error of cross-validation and the root mean square error of calibration were employed, which confirmed the models' accuracy in predicting drug concentrations. When applied to Luporal capsules, the models predicted the content of Tegafur and Uracil accurately, with assay values of 99.44% and 101.77% (PCR) and 98.73% and 102.30% (PLS). The PCR and PLS methods developed in this study were proven to be accurate, precise, and robust for the simultaneous analysis of Tegafur and Uracil in pharmaceutical formulations. These methods offer a reliable approach for routine quality control testing in the pharmaceutical industry.

Key words: Multi linear regression analysis, UV-spectrophotometry, principal component regression, partial least squares, Tegafur, Uracil, Assay.

INTRODUCTION:

Colorectal cancer poses a substantial threat to global health, standing as one of the most prevalent forms of cancer. Each year, it claims nearly 935,000 lives and affects approximately 1.9 million people worldwide. The disease disproportionately impacts individuals aged 50 and above, and its prognosis varies significantly based on the stage at which it is diagnosed. This highlights the critical need for enhanced awareness, early detection, and effective treatment approaches to combat this growing health concern. The disease is more prevalent in developed countries, but its incidence is increasing in low- and middle-income nations, including India, where it is the third most common cancer, with an estimated 80,000 to 90,000 new cases annually. Early detection is crucial for improving outcomes, as late-stage diagnoses, limited awareness, and restricted healthcare access contribute to lower survival rates in countries like India. 5-Fluoro Uracil is one of the most commonly used chemotherapy drugs for colorectal cancer. It works by interfering with the cancer cells' ability to divide and grow. Often given in combination with other drugs (like leucovorin or oxaliplatin), 5-FU is typically used in both adjuvant (post-surgery) and palliative (advanced stages) settings. Tegafur and Uracil combined dosage form which is marketed as a Luporal Capsules is one of the preferred choices for colorectal cancer. The chemical structure of these drugs were represented in figure 1.

A thorough literature survey on the analytical methods for this combination revealed that only few High Performance Liquid Chromatography methods were developed¹⁻⁷. Hence an attempt was made to develop a simple and rapid UV-spectrophotometric methods based on Chemometric models like Principal Component Regression (PCR) and Partial Least Squares Regression. Principal Component Regression (PCR) and Partial Least Squares Regression (PLS) are powerful chemometric tools used in pharmaceutical analysis for the simultaneous estimation of multiple components in complex mixtures⁸⁻²¹. By combining Principal Component Analysis (PCA) and Multiple Linear Regression

(MLR), PCR reduces the dimensionality of spectral data, enabling accurate prediction of drug concentrations. In contrast, PLS considers both spectral data and drug concentrations simultaneously, maximizing covariance to provide better predictive accuracy and effectively handling collinearity. Both PCR and PLS are well-suited for simultaneous drug analysis, such as quantifying Tegafur and Uracil in capsule formulations without physical separation of components. While PLS generally offers more robust and precise results, especially in complex datasets, PCR is a simpler and effective approach for linear relationships. Due to their efficiency and reliability, both methods are widely employed in pharmaceutical quality control and drug formulation analysis

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Instruments and chemicals used

The study employed a Shimadzu UV-1800 double-beam UV-Visible spectrophotometer, paired with 1cm quartz and glass cells, and linked to a computer utilizing UV Probe software for data collection. An electronic balance, specifically the Shimadzu AY 220, facilitated precise sample weighing. Additionally, specialized software, including Unscrambler X version 10.5, enabled advanced chemometric analysis, while Microsoft Excel 2010 supported statistical and regression analysis, providing a comprehensive toolkit for data examination. The study utilized pure samples of Tegafur and Uracil, sourced from Tokyo Chemical Industry Chemicals (India) Pvt. Ltd., Chennai. Methanol (AR grade) was employed as the solvent. Additionally, Luporal Capsules (manufactured by Lupin Ltd.), a marketed formulation containing 100mg Tegafur and 224mg Uracil, was used as the sample for estimating the drug concentrations in the present study.

Construction of calibration curves and recording of UV-spectral data

UV spectra of Tegafur and Uracil were recorded in the range of 200-400 nm using methanol as a solvent, and their absorption maxima were found to be 270 nm and 258 nm, respectively. Tegafur and Uracil standard stock solutions were prepared in concentrations ranging from 3 to 18 $\mu\text{g/mL}$, and their calibration curves were established. To develop the models, mixtures of Tegafur and

Uracil were prepared in various ratios, as detailed in Table 1, and their UV-VIS spectra were recorded between 200 and 400 nm using water as a reference. The spectral data were then analyzed within a specific wavelength range of 225-300 nm, with measurements taken at 5 nm intervals, allowing for a detailed examination of the compounds' spectral characteristics.

Table No.1: Dataset for Calibration and validation modelling for PCR and PLS methods

Calibration Dataset(concentration in µg/mL)			Validation Dataset(concentration in µg/mL)		
Mix No.	Tegafur	Uracil	Mix No.	Tegafur	Uracil
1	6	12	12	12	12
2	6	15	13	12	15
3	6	18	14	12	18
4	9	6	15	15	18
5	9	9	16	18	3
6	9	12	17	18	6
7	9	18	18	18	18
8	12	9	19	9	15
9	15	9	20	9	18
10	15	15			
11	15	9			

Application of multivariate chemometric PCR & PLS models

The spectral data of all the prepared standard mixture solutions in the range of 225-300 nm was imported into the UNSCRAMBLER X version 10.5 software (Camo analytics). The standard mixture solutions were split into two groups: one for building the model (calibration dataset) and the other for testing its predictive ability (validation dataset). The Principal Component Regression

and Partial Least Squares models were developed by identifying the ideal number of factors to use, with each model type relying on different mathematical approaches. To assess the models' performance, various statistical metrics were calculated, including measures of error and correlation. The models were then validated using an independent dataset and subsequently applied to analyze the drug formulation, specifically Luporal capsules, at specified concentrations of Tegafur and Uracil.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

Optimization of chemometric PCR & PLS models for the selected drugs

The concentration ranges for constructing calibration curves were selected according to Beer – Lambert's law. For Tegafur and Uracil the concentration ranges used for constructing calibration curves for are 3-18 μ g/mL and 3-18 μ g/mL respectively. The selected concentration ranges for both the drugs yielded good correlation coefficient values. The calibration curves and linearity graphs were represented in the Figures 3,4,5& 6. Tegafur showed linearity with a R² value of 0.9998 and Uracil showed 0.9995 which was very good. The wavelength range selected for the spectral analysis for the mixtures is 225-300 nm with 5 nm data interval).

The data below 224nm was discarded due to the presence of noise and above 299nm was not selected due to presence of infinitesimal absorbance. Data sets (calibration set and validation set) were created and the calibration set was optimized by using optimal factors. The number of PCs in PCR and LVs in PLS were chosen based on the obtained RMSECV values as shown in Table 2 For PCR method, the optimum number of PCs for Tegafur and Uracil was found to be 7 for both the drugs. For PLS method, the optimum number of LVs for was found to be 7 for both the drugs.

The calibration set with the least RMSECV values was optimized for the simultaneous determination of Tegafur and Uracil. PCR & PLS models were constructed by framing 11 standard mixture solutions in the calibration set and the constructed models were analyzed by using statistical parameters. The results obtained by PCR and PLS for the optimized calibration set were

shown in Tables 3 and 4 respectively. RMSEC plots of the predicted and reference values obtained by PCR & PLS models were shown in Figures 4 and 5 respectively.

Table No.2: Cross validation performance metrics of datasets of Tegafur and Uracil

PCR			PLS		
PCs	Tegafur	Uracil	PLs	Tegafur	Uracil
PC-1	4.049	3.748	Factor-1	2.993	2.705
PC-2	0.466	0.466	Factor-2	0.461	0.459
PC-3	0.421	0.303	Factor-3	0.412	0.301
PC-4	0.273	0.272	Factor-4	0.273	0.500
PC-5	0.307	0.259	Factor-5	0.278	0.270
PC-6	0.269	0.257	Factor-6	0.288	0.276
PC-7	0.247	0.248	Factor-7	0.233	0.244

Table No.3: Predicted values for calibration dataset of Tegafur and Uracil by PCR

Calibration mixture	Predicted values ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)		% Recovery	
	Tegafur	Uracil	Tegafur	Uracil
1	6.138	12.101	102.306	100.840
2	5.979	14.883	99.654	99.219
3	6.010	17.989	100.161	99.941
4	8.991	6.016	99.905	100.270
5	8.985	8.817	99.837	97.970
6	8.813	12.140	97.924	101.167
7	9.018	18.071	100.203	100.399
8	12.038	9.035	100.315	100.394

9	15.009	8.982	100.059	99.801
10	15.001	14.918	100.006	99.453
11	18.017	9.048	100.095	100.525
Mean			100.042	99.998
SD			0.951	0.843
RMSEC			0.072	0.092
Correlation coefficient (R^2)			0.9996	0.999
RMSECV			0.269	0.272

Table No.4: Predicted Values for calibration set of Tegafur and Uracil by PLS

Calibration mixture	Predicted values ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)		% Recovery	
	Tegafur	Uracil	Tegafur	Uracil
1	6.080	12.096	101.331	100.797
2	6.010	14.874	100.164	99.159
3	5.962	18.021	99.374	100.119
4	8.991	6.031	99.895	100.515
5	8.949	8.880	99.429	98.670
6	8.965	12.080	99.616	100.664
7	9.021	18.022	100.239	100.120
8	12.022	9.025	100.181	100.281
9	14.987	8.968	99.911	99.646
10	14.988	14.981	99.919	99.875
11	18.026	9.02	100.143	100.245
Mean			100.018	100.008

SD	0.504	0.612
RMSEC	0.504	0.612
Correlation coefficient (R^2)	0.035	0.067
RMSECV	0.9999	0.9996

The performance of the PCR and PLS models was evaluated, and the results showed a good agreement between the actual and predicted values, confirming the models' accuracy. The statistical analysis revealed that the mean, standard deviation, and other relevant parameters were within acceptable ranges, indicating the reliability of the models. Based on these findings, the calibration set was deemed suitable for analyzing the commercial formulation, demonstrating the potential for practical application.

Validation of chemometric PCR & PLS models for the selected drugs

To assess the predictive ability of the Principal Component Regression (PCR) and Partial Least Squares (PLS) models, an external validation was performed using a test set of 9 standard mixture solutions not included in the calibration set. The optimized models were applied to the test set to predict the concentrations of Tegafur and Uracil. The accuracy and Root Mean Square Error of Prediction (RMSEP) values, presented in Tables 5 and 6, respectively, were used to evaluate the models' predictive performance. The accuracy of the PCR and PLS models is visually represented in Figures 6 and 7, respectively.

The results obtained from the test set revealed that both the developed models were found to be accurate. Figures 8 & 9 showed the closeness of actual values and predicted values by PCR & PLS models respectively, which indicated their good predictive ability.

Table No.5: Predicted Values obtained for validation dataset of Tegafur and Uracil by PCR

Calibration mixture	Predicted values ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	% Recovery

	Tegafur	Uracil	Tegafur	Uracil
1	12.59	11.412	104.913	95.102
2	12.548	14.638	104.563	97.586
3	12.593	18.150	104.940	100.831
4	15.461	17.243	103.077	95.796
5	17.100	3.142	94.99944	104.733
6	17.198	5.929	95.542	98.821
7	17.144	17.217	95.243	95.652
8	9.445	15.053	104.940	100.350
9	9.406	17.984	104.515	99.913
Mean			101.415	98.754
SD			4.386	2.926
%RSD			4.325	2.963
Root mean square of Prediction (RMSEP)			0.647	0.436

Table No.6: Predicted Values obtained for validation dataset of Tegafur and Uracil by PLS

Calibration mixture	Predicted values ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)		% Recovery	
	Tegafur	Uracil	Tegafur	Uracil
1	12.559	11.393	104.655	95.107
2	12.509	14.675	104.246	97.834
3	12.547	18.194	104.562	101.077
4	15.457	17.247	103.045	95.819
5	16.999	3.130	94.999	104.320
6	17.207	5.919	95.596	98.645
7	17.145	17.216	95.248	95.644

8	9.408	15.089	104.532	100.592
9	9.365	18.025	104.051	100.141
Mean			101.215	98.768
SD			4.222	2.870
%RSD			4.171	2.904
Root mean square of Prediction (RMSEP)			0.645	0.438

Assay of the Luporal Capsule dosage form

The validated Principal Component Regression (PCR) and Partial Least Squares (PLS) models were utilized to predict the concentrations of Tegafur and Uracil in a marketed formulation. The results, presented in Tables 7 and 8, showed that the predicted concentrations of Tegafur (5 $\mu\text{g/mL}$) and Uracil (11.2 $\mu\text{g/mL}$) were within acceptable limits. A summary of the statistical parameters for the calibration set, test set, and marketed formulation, obtained using both PCR and PLS models, is provided in Table 9.

Table No.7: Quantification results obtained for the Luporal Capsules by PCR

Calibration mixture	Predicted values ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)		% Recovery	
	Tegafur	Uracil	Tegafur	Uracil
1	4.997	11.399	99.944	101.773
2	5.012	11.414	100.244	101.911
3	4.982	11.383	99.645	101.635
Mean			99.944	101.773
SD			0.244	0.113
%RSD			0.245	0.111

Table No.8: Quantification results obtained for the Luporal Capsules by PLS

Calibration mixture	Predicted values ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)		% Recovery	
	Tegafur	Uracil	Tegafur	Uracil
1	4.937	11.458	98.737	102.302
2	4.952	11.473	99.044	102.437
3	4.921	11.443	98.429	102.168
Mean			98.737	102.302
SD			0.251	0.10964
%RSD			0.254	0.107

Table No.9: Summary Results obtained for Tegafur and Uracil by PCR & PLS

Statistical parameters	PCR		PLS	
	Tegafur	Uracil	Tegafur	Uracil
Concentration range ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	3-18 $\mu\text{g/mL}$	3-18 $\mu\text{g/mL}$	3-18 $\mu\text{g/mL}$	3-18 $\mu\text{g/mL}$
No. of factors	7	7	7	7
R ²	0.9996	0.999	0.9999	0.9996
RMSEC	0.072	0.092	0.035	0.067
RMSECV	0.269	0.272	0.288	0.500
RMSEP	0.647	0.436	0.645	0.438
Calibration set (Mean \pm SD)	100.042	99.997	100.018	100.008
Validation set (Mean \pm SD)	101.415	98.754	101.215	98.768
Assay % (Mean \pm SD)	99.944	101.773	98.737	102.302

CONCLUSION:

An attempt was made to develop multi linear regression analysis methods in UV-spectrophotometry based on principal component regression and partial least squares for the simultaneous analysis of Tegafur and Uracil in capsule dosage form. The developed analytical methods are novel, accurate, precise, robust and can be employed for the analysis of these compounds in the dosage forms.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare no conflict of interest

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Figures

Fig. 1: Tegafur and Uracil chemical structures

Fig. 2: Calibration curve of Tegafur&Uracil

Fig. 3: Linearity graph of Tegafur and Uracil

Fig. 4: PCR Model Performance: RMSECV Plot for Tegafur and Uracil

Fig. 5: Predicted vs. Reference Values: RMSEC Plot for PCR Model

Fig. 6: PLSModel Performance: RMSECV Plot for Tegafur and Uracil

Fig. 7: Predicted vs. Reference Values: RMSEC Plot for PLS Model

Fig. 8: PCR Model Predictions: Actual vs. Predicted Concentrations

Fig. 8: PLS Model Predictions: Actual vs. Predicted Concentrations